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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12800446>

THE CREATIVE PATH OF THE VIENNA STRAUSS FESTIVAL ORCHESTRA

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ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПУТЬ ВЕНСКОГО ФЕСТИВАЛЬНОГО ОРКЕСТРА ШТРАУСА

Abstract.

The Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra is one of the world's leading and most prestigious orchestral ensembles. Until the 1840s, there was no special concert orchestra in Vienna. In 1833, the German composer and conductor Franz Paul Lachner created the first concert orchestra composed of members of the Vienna Opera Orchestra and organized four concerts. In 1860, German conductor Eckert Karl Anton, head of the palace opera collective, organized the first big concert with these performers, and these concerts were held regularly.

Until 1933, the Vienna Philharmonic Orchestra had no artistic director and no long-term contracts were signed with conductors. Every year, a conductor was appointed by voting. However, some conductors were elected to lead the orchestra for several years in a row. Thus, during the years 1860-1875, the leader and conductor of the orchestra was Otto Dessof. In 1875, the flourishing period of the orchestra begun with the arrival of the talented opera-symphonic conductor Hans Richter. According to musicians, under Richter's leadership, the orchestra experienced its golden age. Until 1898, Hans Richter led the orchestra. From 1898 to 1901, Gustav Mahler was appointed conductor. Mahler continued Richter's traditions, paying special attention to the ensemble sound and conducting rehearsals himself. In 1906, with the arrival of the German composer and conductor Richard Strauss, the orchestra was revived, and rehearsals began on more complex works. The repertoire included the sophisticated compositions of Y. Haydn, W. Mozart, L. Beethoven, F. Schubert, R. Schumann, I. Brahms, and G. Mahler. In 1978, at the initiative of Peter Gutt, the orchestra officially began operating as the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra. Today, the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra continues to lead globally, maintaining its prominent status nearly two centuries since its inception.

Аннотация.

Симфонический оркестр прошел длительный путь развития. Термин оркестр происходит от греческого слова оркестра, обозначающего в греческом театре X века до нашей эры круглую площадку с жертвенником посередине-место для выступления хора. Конец XVII-начало XVIII веков были временем бурного развития и широкого распространения оркестровой культуры. Первый концерт Венского филармонического оркестра состоялся 28 марта 1842 под управлением О. Николаи. В состав Венского филармонического оркестра вошли музыканты оркестра Венской оперы. Венский филармонический оркестр занял видное место в музыкальной жизни страны. С 1860 оркестр, как правило, выступал под управлением своих постоянных руководителей-О. Дессофа, Х. Рихтера, Г. Малера. Рихтер и Малер значительно расширили репертуар, включив произведения композиторов разных стран: А. Дворжак, Б. Сметана, З. Фибих, П. Чайковский, К. Сен-Санс и др. Во главе с Рихтером Венский филармонический оркестр впервые выехал на гастроли в Зальцбург. С 1917 года Венский филармонический оркестр-официальный оркестр Зальцбургских фестивалей. Начиная со своего основания в 1978 году, Венский Штраус-Фестиваль Оркестр завоевал международное признание, выступая в именитых концертных залах с оригинальной интерпретацией венской музыки.

Keywords: orchestra, Richard Strauss, Vienna, symphonic, opera music, symphony, collective, musical instruments, Peter Gutt, conducting, violinist.

Ключевые слова: оркестр, Рихард Штраус, Вена, симфонический, оперная музыка, симфония, коллектив, музыкальные инструменты, Петер Гутт, дирижирование, скрипач.

The Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra is one of the world's leading and most prestigious orchestral ensembles. To present his creative path, let's first consider the history of the symphony orchestra and its influence on the creation of the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra:

In the second half of the 18th century, the first symphonic orchestra was created by Joseph Haydn. At first, the composition of the orchestra was relatively limited, the group of brass instruments included horns and trumpets, and the group of percussion instruments included only timpani.

This collective, which consisted of twelve members, was known as a small symphony orchestra. Orchestra comes from the Greek word "orchestra". In ancient Greece, the front part of the stage, closer to the audience, was called "orchestra". [M. Umudov, 2015, p. 80]

During the performance, the choir sang and danced here. Later, a group of musicians began to sit here. Gradually, that group was given the name of orchestra. Later, this term began to represent not only a group of musicians, but also instrumental music collectives.

The composition of both the opera orchestra and the later called "symphonic" orchestra was not fully established until the last years of the 16th century. Thus, the composition of the orchestra was exposed to a number of influences during its existence and changed frequently. The composition of the orchestra changed depending on the requirements of the performance in the opera theater and one or another group of musicians in the concert hall.

The composition of the orchestra was updated based on the opinion of both the composer and the orchestra director. The first orchestras were completely different from modern symphony orchestras.

Until the beginning of the 17th century, there was no full-fledged orchestra, which included a violin (7-8 players), a viola (3-4 players), a lyre, a harp, a flute, a piccolo flute, a lute, a trombone (2 players), a gabyo (2 performer), organ and harpsichord were included. Strings, wind and percussion instruments had difficulty in harmonizing with each other.

The famous Italian composer Claudio Monteverdi was the first to understand the duties and artistic possibilities of each instrument in the orchestra. In his operas, he divided the orchestra into strings, wind instruments and instruments that accompanied the melody or play the main theme. These reforms showed that K. Monteverdi was a great innovator. He said: "As a result of the new reforms, it is possible to achieve a fuller sound in the orchestra" [Rosenschild K. 1973, p. 209]

In the following years, the head of the Naples school, Alessandro Scarlatti, further transformed the orchestra. He included two horns in the orchestra, separated the duties of strings and wind instruments, and placed the strings in the front row as the leading instruments of the orchestra.

In the first half of the 18th century, the development of the orchestra was mainly improved by the work of three genius composers: Jean-Philippe Rameau, Johann Sebastian Bach and Georg Friedrich Handel. With the development of musical art and the creation of the first important operas, composers began to compose works for various ensembles and orchestras. To achieve a uniform tempo in the collective performance of the works, it was necessary to control the orchestras.

At the end of the 18th century, the orchestra entered a new stage of development, and the composition of the orchestra was established with the appropriate musical instruments. The orchestra expanded to include two clarinets, flutes, three trombones, drums, cymbals, and a triangle, in addition to the flute, gabyo, and bassoons.

The lute, theorb, and crwth instruments that were previously used left the orchestra, and the harp was for special occasions. The crota was a five-stringed instrument widespread in Europe in the 8th century. M. Chulaki writes: "In the 8th century, the crwth instrument played with five strings and a bow was very widespread in Europe. The Crotta instrument was a fretless instrument. Stringed instruments with frets began to spread from the 14th century, and one of the first representatives of stringed instruments was the lute. Crotta and lute performed in all orchestras operating in this period" [Chulaki M. 1972, p. 3]

Orchestra management required more complex methods, a conductor was needed. Thus, more experienced and competent musicians, such as harpsichord players and first violinists, began to perform the function of conductor, playing together with the orchestra members

Sometimes the first violinist would stand and give instructions to the orchestra through the bow, so that the players could clearly understand him. This method proved itself in opera concerts, and finally several methods contrasted with modern conducting art emerged.

All the changes in the orchestra in the opera are closely related to the name of composer Willibald Gluck, and in symphonic music, Franz Joseph Haydn and Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart. The orchestra they created laid the foundation of the classical symphony orchestra.

At the beginning of the 19th century, Ludwig Van Beethoven greatly expanded the orchestra, adding several idiophones and membranophones to its composition. The initiative to enrich the orchestra with new instruments was successfully continued. He gave a special place to expressive sound in the orchestra, emphasizing that the orchestra is the most valuable and necessary tool for expressing beautiful music, saying: "The beautiful music played by the symphony orchestra should penetrate the inner world of people and awaken their inner world. In this way, the orchestra should help us" [I. Prikhorova. Moscow, 1973, p. 65]

The role of the German composer and conductor Richard Wagner in the formation of the symphony orchestra should be emphasized. He brought innovations to the art of conducting and the orchestra. For the first time, Richard Wagner conducted by facing the orchestra, and this innovation quickly spread to other countries. [Wagner R. Moscow, 1974, 199 p.]. This initiative gave impetus to the development of the symphony orchestra, as performers could see the conductor's gestures more clearly, positively affecting the sound timbre.

Since the 1950s, the American arrangement has been applied to the symphony orchestra. In this arrangement, violins are placed on the left side of the stage, violas in the center, cellos and double basses on the right, woodwind and brass instruments in the center, and percussion at the back. This arrangement ensures that the orchestra's performance sounds more harmonious.

The Gewandhaus Orchestra (Germany), London Philharmonic Orchestra (England), Boston, Philadelphia Symphony Orchestra (USA), Russian Grand Symphony Orchestra and Vienna Philharmonic Orchestra (Austria) are considered the most famous orchestras in the world. Their activities have been significant achievements in world music culture [Bilkent University Faculty of Music and Performing Arts. 2010. 18 p.].

Now let's take a look at the history of the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra:

Until the 1840s, there was no special concert orchestra in Vienna. In 1833, the German composer and conductor Franz Paul Lachner created the first concert orchestra composed of members of the Vienna Opera Orchestra and organized four concerts. However, the orchestra's activity did not last long because this idea was not supported. Ten years later, Karl Otto Nikolai managed to implement this idea. On March 28, 1842, Nikolai organized the first concert orchestra consisting of members of the Vienna State Opera Orchestra in the Hofburg Palace. Until 1860, the composition and repertoire of the orchestra were not fully established, so the number of concerts held was quite small.

In 1860, German conductor Eckert Karl Anton, head of the palace opera collective, organized the first big concert with these performers, and these concerts were held regularly.

Until 1933, the Vienna Philharmonic Orchestra had no artistic director and no long-term contracts were signed with conductors. Every year, a conductor was appointed by voting. However, some conductors were elected to lead the orchestra for several years in a row. Thus, during the years 1860-1875, the leader and conductor of the orchestra was Otto Dessof. In 1875, the flourishing period of the orchestra begun with the arrival of the talented opera-symphonic conductor Hans Richter. According to musicians, under Richter's leadership, the orchestra experienced its golden age.

H. Richter expanded the composition of the orchestra and enriched the repertoire: works by R. Wagner, A. Bruckner, I. Brahms, F. Liszt were included and performed. The orchestra often gives concerts and was highly appreciated by the residents and guests of the capital. H. Richter included Brahms' Second and Third symphonies, Bruckner's Eighth symphony, and Tchaikovsky's violin concerto in the repertoire, holding their premieres. These concerts were sold out, and the audience enjoyed listening to these works performed by the orchestra. As a result of Richter's high-level communication with the orchestra's soloist-violinist Adolf Brodsky, Tchaikovsky's violin concerto was interpreted with great virtuosity. Richter paid special attention to the ensemble sound in the orchestra, seeing success in its clean and expressive sound.

The musicians of the orchestra agreed with his ideas and worked on themselves to reveal the character of the works, dynamism, and metrorhythmic accuracy. Richter also paid special attention to discipline, not allowing performers to avoid rehearsals without valid reasons. Thus, strict rules of discipline were formed, and the orchestra developed day by day. During Richter's leadership, the orchestra's first concert tours began.

In 1877, the orchestra's first concert in Salzburg was held with great success.

Until 1898, Hans Richter led the orchestra. From 1898 to 1901, Gustav Mahler was appointed conductor. Mahler continued Richter's traditions, paying special attention to the ensemble sound and conducting rehearsals himself. In 1900, under Mahler's leadership, the orchestra performed for the first time at the World Exhibition in Paris, winning the approval of the entire musical community. Although Mahler led the orchestra, Richter regularly supervised the repertoire, intonation, and interpretation issues. The orchestra's performance in Paris was under Richter's supervision, and the musical works sounded even more colorful and enriched with different timbres.

Hans Richter and Gustav Mahler managed to expand the repertoire by including the works of various national composers: A. Dvorak, B. Smetana, Z. Fibix, P. Tchaikovsky, K. Saint-Saëns.

Until 1927, Felix Weingartner led the orchestra without significant progress. Other conductors and composer-conductors such as Brahms, Wagner, Bruckner, and Verdi worked with the orchestra at certain times. Since 1927, the orchestra has been led by Wilhelm Furtwängler. However, musicians such as Franz Schalk, Artur Nikisch, Erich Kleiber, Bruno Walter, Arturo Toscanini, Carl Schuricht, Hans Knappertsbusch, Victor de Sabata, Clemens Krauss, and Karl Böhm also worked with the orchestra.

The development of the art of music and the creation of new works required the orchestra's composition and repertoire to be renewed.

In 1906, with the arrival of the German composer and conductor Richard Strauss, the orchestra was revived, and rehearsals began on more complex works. The repertoire included the sophisticated compositions of Y. Haydn, W. Mozart, L. Beethoven, F. Schubert, R. Schumann, I. Brahms, and G. Mahler.

Richard Strauss succeeded in further expanding the orchestra, enriching the repertoire with new works, and extending concert tours to foreign countries. He took significant steps in the formation of the orchestra, inviting experienced musicians from the Vienna Opera House. By adding horns, trumpets, and German clarinets to the woodwinds and brass sections, the number of performers increased to 120. Notable violinists included Willy Boskovski, Arnold Rose, and Fris Zedlak; viola players were Bachrich Sigismund and Ernst Moraves; cellists were Friedrich Buxbaum, Reinhold Hummer, and Franz Schmidt; horn players were Gottfried von Freiber and Karl Stiegler; clarinetists were Alfred Boskovski, Leopold Vlach, and Thomas Jobstl; trombonists were Bousfield Yen and Vladimir Orloff; tuba player was Walter Hilgers; and bassoonist was Karl Elberger. Each musician understood the intricacies of classical music and aimed to touch the hearts and tastes of the audience.

Since 1917, the Vienna Philharmonic Orchestra has been the official orchestra of the Salzburg Festival, a success achieved under Strauss's leadership. The orchestra, performing vibrant works annually at the Salzburg Festival, soon became the world's leading orchestra. Concurrently, the orchestra was actively involved

in staging operas in Vienna and Salzburg, further expanding its tour arena.

R. Strauss led the orchestra until 1944 and achieved greater recognition for the ensemble worldwide. Richard Strauss served as both conductor and advisor to the musicians. He assisted orchestra members whenever necessary, treating them with special care and fostering a friendly atmosphere within the team. As a result, the orchestra held Strauss in high regard, faithfully executing his ideas as conductor and leader. In honor of his contributions, the orchestra was later named after him.

One unique feature of the orchestra historically was its all-male composition, which persisted until the 20th century when female performers began to join.

In 1978, at the initiative of Peter Gutt, the orchestra officially began operating as the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra. Gutt, a graduate of the University of Vienna in instrumental performance and a student of David Oistrakh at the Moscow State Conservatory, gained international acclaim as a violinist with the Viennese trio, winning first place in a Munich competition.

Gutt later pursued a career as both a violinist and conductor, performing with renowned orchestras such as the London Royal Philharmonic, Tokyo Symphony Orchestra, and San Francisco Symphony Orchestra. Devoting much of his life to the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra, Gutt led performances worldwide, including in Asia, Europe, Russia, China, South Korea, and Japan.

He performed at prestigious venues such as the Cologne Philharmonic, Munich's Hercules Hall, Tokyo's Santori Hall, Seoul Art Center, Moscow Music House, and others. Gutt expanded the orchestra's repertoire to include works like Y. Heidi's Symphony No. 44 in E minor and V. Mozart's Concerto No. 2 for flute and orchestra in D major.

The Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra, under Peter Gutt's direction, embarks on annual concert tours worldwide, captivating millions of listeners and enriching their artistic tastes.

Gutt introduced innovations in modern conducting, applying techniques such as dancing with female vocal soloists during performances, facing the audience while conducting, entertaining with clapping, and incorporating dance elements. He even conducted with a bow while playing the violin, revolutionizing the art form.

Peter Gutt aimed for a freer, more creative approach to conducting, believing in methods that engage and entertain listeners. In his interviews, he stated, "We

aim to interpret as Strauss did in his time. Strauss conquered the world with this orchestra." [8]

On November 20, 2013, the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra gained global acclaim with a high-level performance at the PI Tchaikovsky Concert Hall in Moscow, performing all symphonies by Ludwig Van Beethoven in four concerts supported by the "Music Olympia" Foundation. [4].

The orchestra has performed numerous times in various countries, including Azerbaijan, where it garnered great affection from the people. At a concert in the Heydar Aliyev Center on April 28, 2022, conductor Peter Gutt impressed audiences with memorable interpretations. [3].

The program featured works by Johann Strauss, known as the "King of the Waltz," and other renowned composers. The Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra is eagerly anticipated annually in Azerbaijan, having become beloved by the Azerbaijani people.

The orchestra regularly participates in the Strauss Festival in Europe and opens the prestigious Vienna Ball Festival each January 1st. Its concert schedule is planned years in advance. Annually on New Year's Eve, the orchestra inaugurates the concert season at Vienna's Musikverein Golden Hall, an event watched by 70 TV channels, 300 radio stations, and 50 million people. In summer, the orchestra performs in Schönbrunn Palace Park, delighting Vienna's residents.

Today, the Vienna Strauss Festival Orchestra continues to lead globally, maintaining its prominent status nearly two centuries since its inception.

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